

Confinement-induced one-dimensional ferroelectric polymer arrays

Mari-Cruz García-Gutiérrez^{*,†}, Amelia Linares[†], Jaime J. Hernández[†], Daniel R. Rueda[†], Tiberio A. Ezquerro[†], Pedro Poza[§] and Richard J. Davies[‡]

[†] Instituto de Estructura de la Materia, CSIC, Serrano 121, 28006 Madrid, Spain

[§] Departamento de Ciencia e Ingeniería de Materiales, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, 28933 Móstoles, Madrid, Spain.

[‡] ESRF, B.P. 220, F-38043 Grenoble Cedex, France

* Phone: +34 915616800; fax: +34 915645557; e-mail: maricruz@iem.cfmac.csic.es

Abstract

This work demonstrates the use of wetting nanoporous alumina template with polymer solution to produce arrays of isolated Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) ferroelectric γ -type nanorods supported within a nonpolar α structure film. The method is based upon a crystal phase transition which occurs due to PVDF confinement within alumina nanoporous. The system was studied using scanning X-ray microdiffraction (μ -XRD) which allows the solid-solid phase transition from the α non polar crystal form (bulk) to the γ polar ferroelectric form (nanorod array) to be spatially resolved, as well as providing crystallinity and orientation information. The results reveal that the interaction between polymer chains and the porous membrane's walls imposes a flat-on lamella growth along the nanorods long axis, whilst improving crystal orientation.

Arrays of polymer nanostructures exhibit an interesting behavior which makes them promising candidates for use in photonics, electronics, mechanical, and biomedical devices¹⁻³. High aspect ratio (length/diameter) one-dimensional (1D) nanostructures are also appropriate for studying size-dependent processes with length scales comparable to the nanostructures' size, such as phase separation in block copolymers, or crystalline textures⁴.

Material properties strongly depend upon molecular order and orientation. Crystallization is one of the simplest molecular-scale self-organization processes capable to control spatially the ordering of molecules and hence to tune the properties of partially crystalline polymer nanostructures, as they will largely depend upon the properties of their crystalline domains. Recent studies of polymer crystallization in restricted geometries shed some light on the possibility of controlling crystallization at the nanoscale. Some of the methods used allow well defined nanostructures to be generated, such as via microphase separated domains of semicrystalline block copolymers⁵⁻⁷, nanoimprint lithography (NIL)^{2, 8} and template wetting^{1, 3}. The technique of template wetting is based upon the fact that polymer melts and polymer solutions tend to wet the walls of nanoporous templates if the walls exhibit a high surface energy^{9, 10}. The advantage of this technique, using porous anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) as a template, is the high versatility of the method, allowing the preparation of both ordered arrays of low aspect ratio 1D polymer nanostructures and high aspect ratio free 1D nanostructures^{3, 11}.

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) exhibits a pronounced polymorphism, transforming between several crystal forms under certain conditions. Chains free from configurational defects can crystallize into regular chain conformations. Particularly, for PVDF there are three known conformations¹²: 1) a consecutive all trans, TTTT

sequence, provides good ferroelectric polarization, 2) an alternating trans and gauche conformation, TGT, leads to almost null polarization because of the internal cancellation of dipole ordering, and 3) another conformation that imparts ferroelectric polarization with a TTTG sequence. In PVDF there are several crystalline structures induced by the regular chain packing of these configurations, with α , β , and γ corresponding to TGT, TTTT, and TTTG sequences, respectively¹³⁻¹⁷. The successful development of ferroelectric polymer devices depends on the effective fabrication of polar ferroelectric crystalline structures such as β and γ ^{2, 18}.

Although a number of papers have been published on the topic of polymorphic crystal transitions of PVDF specimens prepared from either the melt or solution¹⁸⁻²⁴, most of them have focused on methods of achieving polar β or γ structures, such as by using mechanical stretching, high compression, hygroscopic salts, rate of cooling and heating, microimprinting and solvent evaporation.

The present study shows a technique that produces arrays of isolated PVDF ferroelectric γ -type nanorods connected by a supporting film having a nonpolar α structure. The method is based on a phase transition due to PVDF confinement within nanopores and its interaction with the walls of the AAO membrane, as revealed by scanning X-ray microdiffraction (μ -XRD) using synchrotron light²⁵. This powerful tool reveals the spatial evolution of the solid-solid phase transition from the α non polar crystal form (bulk) to the γ polar ferroelectric form (nanorod array). It also allows the degree of crystallinity, and the crystal orientation to be investigated, providing information over multiple length scales simultaneously.

In order to prepare polymer nanostructures by solution template wetting, alumina membranes with pore sizes of 150-200 nm were used, supplied by Whatman Inc. A solution containing 30 wt % PVDF ($M_w = 288$ kg/mol) in N,N-dimethylacetamide

(Sigma-Aldrich) was prepared. For solution wetting, the AAO membrane was placed on the top of a drop of the solution wetting and subsequently dried at 60 °C under vacuum for 20 hours. In order to characterize the morphology of the polymer nanoarray the template was then removed. Parallel aligned PVDF nanofibers were revealed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), as shown in Figure 1(a).

X-ray microdiffraction experiments using synchrotron radiation have been carried out at the ID13 beamline (ESRF). Scanning μ -XRD with a 1 μ m diameter beam was accomplished along the cross section of the sample (Figure 1(b)) with diffraction patterns collected at regular intervals between the residual PVDF film (bulk) and the nanorod array. The sample's nanorod axis was carefully aligned perpendicular to the X-ray beam, and the 2D-diffraction patterns were recorded in transmission geometry. Figure 2(a) shows the diffraction pattern of the residual PVDF film and Figure 2(b) that of PVDF nanorods inside porous alumina. The small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) region of the patterns has been enlarged and presented with the figure as insets.

It is worth noting that while for the bulk (Figure 2(a)) the SAXS signal is anisotropic, with a greater intensity on the meridian corresponding to a long period of about 8 nm related to the nanostructure of semicrystalline polymers consisting of a stacked lamellar crystals separated by amorphous layers²⁶, for the PVDF nanorods (Figure 2(b)) the SAXS intensity is concentrated on the equator corresponding to correlation lengths related to the pores of the AAO membrane, but no signal of the polymer long period is observed in this case.

The information obtained from the wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) is complementary to SAXS due to the difference in length scales being probed. At first sight, the WAXS signal from the PVDF nanorods appears to suggest a highly oriented crystalline pattern compared to that of the residual PVDF film. Further analysis of the

WAXS patterns reveals, however, that the differences between patterns (a) and (b) in Figure 2 are not only due to orientation effects, as was reported to occur in PVDF nanotubes and nanorods prepared by melt-wetting^{4, 27}, but also due to a crystal phase transformation. Azimuthally integrating the WAXS region of patterns 2(a) and 2(b) the corresponding 1-D intensity profiles were obtained and are presented in Figure 3. These have been indexed according to the α pseudo-orthorhombic ($a=4.96 \text{ \AA}$, $b=9.64 \text{ \AA}$, $c=4.62 \text{ \AA}$, and $\beta=90^\circ$)¹⁴ and γ monoclinic ($a=4.96 \text{ \AA}$, $b=9.67 \text{ \AA}$, $c=9.20 \text{ \AA}$, and $\beta=93^\circ$)^{16, 17} crystalline forms respectively.

From diffraction patterns collected between the residual polymer film and the nanorod array, the degree of crystallinity can be spatially investigated (Figure 4). This has been calculated from the equation $X_c = \sum I_c / \sum (I_a + I_c)$ where I_c is the integrated area underneath the crystalline peaks and I_a is the integrated area of the amorphous halo, estimated by the peak-fitting of the 1-D intensity profiles obtained at each position along the sample cross section. Figure 4(a) shows that the degree of crystallinity is reduced from about 30% in the residual film to about 20% in the nanorod array. The partial hindering of crystallization due to a confinement of polymer chains within porous alumina membranes infiltrated by melt-wetting has been already reported^{28, 29}. The spatial evolution of the abrupt solid-solid phase transition from the α non polar crystal form (bulk) to the γ polar ferroelectric form (nanorod array) is also shown in Figure 4(b), and was estimated from the relation between the integrated area underneath the α and γ crystal peaks, $X_\gamma = \sum I_\gamma / \sum (I_\alpha + I_\gamma)$. The present data also show that the degree of crystal orientation increases due to confinement. This is demonstrated by a decreasing azimuthal full width at half maximum (FWHM) for the

020 reflection when moving from the residual film to the nanorod array, as shown in Figure 4(c).

From the pronounced crystal texture exhibited in Figure 2(b), and once the reflections have been indexed, it can be seen that the strong 020 reflection is concentrated on the equator. This indicates that inside the porous alumina the *b*-axis of the crystal unit cell is aligned parallel to the long axis of the PVDF nanorods with the *a*- and *c*-axes, (being close to perpendicular from one another), lying on the cross section of the nanorrod, perpendicular to its long axis as shown in Figure 5. In Figure 2(a) meanwhile, the orientation of crystal lamella is revealed by a greater SAXS intensity on the meridian. This indicates that in the residual polymer film the polymer chain direction (which corresponds to the *c*-axis of the unit cell) is preferentially oriented perpendicular to the surface of the AAO membrane (free of pores) and hence parallel to the long axis of the PVDF nanorods. This suggests that crystallites grow preferentially flat-on (Figure 5). This switch of crystal orientation from the residual film to the nanorrod array provides direct experimental evidence that the interaction of porous alumina membrane walls, when wetted by the polymer (Figure 1), plays a determinant role in the crystal orientation of polymer lamellae into the nanorods. It is in agreement with previous experiments in which crystallization takes place either in presence of a residual polymer film or without it^{4, 27-29}. This result is also in agreement with simulations of polymer crystallization confined in rigid nanotubes³⁰, when the nanotube walls are highly wetted by the polymer the molecular simulations predict that the growth of flat-on lamellar crystals is favored.

In conclusion, the present work shows that solution template wetting is a versatile method to produce arrays of isolated ferroelectric γ -type nanorods connected by a paraelectric α structure supporting film. The AAO walls template polymer

crystallization orienting the lamellar crystals flat-on growing along the nanorods long axis. The method is based upon a phase transition induced by the confinement of PVDF into nanoporous and by its interaction with the walls of the AAO membrane. The advantage of this method using porous anodic aluminum oxide as a template is the high versatility of the method, allowing the preparation of both arrays of ferroelectric nanorods supported by a paraelectric polymer film for applications mainly in photonics and electronics and high aspect ratio free 1D nanostructures, when removing the residual film, for applications in sensors based on piezoelectric properties.

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Supporting Information Available: Detailed experimental procedures for the sample preparation, characterization and evidences of phase transition. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. SEM images of PVDF nanostructures prepared by solution template wetting: (a) side and top (inset) views showing the nanorod morphology when the alumina template has been removed; (b) cross section of a sample fractured in liquid nitrogen, the inset is a magnified image of the interface between the residual PVDF film (right) and the nanorod array (left) into the alumina membrane.

Figure 2. 2D-diffraction patterns recorded in transmission geometry: (a) diffraction pattern of the residual PVDF film and (b) diffraction pattern of PVDF nanorods inside porous alumina. Note that the vertical shadow comes from the few millimeters thick sample along the beam path. The small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) region of the patterns has been enlarged and presented as insets.

Figure 3. 1-D intensity profiles calculated by the azimuthal integration of the 2D-diffraction patterns presented in figure 2. The hkl indexes of reflections corresponding to the α (a) and γ (b) crystalline forms are shown.

Figure 4. Spatial evolution of three different magnitudes, from the residual polymer film (bulk) to the nanorod array: (a) degree of crystallinity; (b) fraction of the ferroelectric γ form; (c) full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the reflection 020.

Figure 5. Schematic proposed model for the switch of crystal orientation from the residual film to the nanorod array. Inside the porous alumina the b -axis of the crystal unit cell is aligned parallel to the long axis of the PVDF nanorods with the a - and c -axes lying on the cross section of the nanorod, perpendicular to its long axis. While in the residual polymer film the c -axis of the unit cell is preferentially oriented perpendicular to the surface of the AAO membrane (free of pores) and hence parallel to the long axis of the PVDF nanorods. This suggests that crystallites grow preferentially flat-on.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5